

Supplementary Information for: "WingSegment: A Computer Vision-Based Hybrid Approach for Insect Wing Image Segmentation and 3D Printing"

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This file contains additional information pertaining to the development of WingSegment. Within this document, you will find detailed insights into the validation process of WingSegment, including comprehensive descriptions of the developed codes. Additionally, there is an in-depth illustration of the Graphical User Interface (GUI). To showcase the performance of WingSegment, we have included 3D printed models of three other complex wings from Damselfly, Dragonfly, and Locust.

Furthermore, this study encompasses several supplementary files stored in the Zenodo repository, accessible via the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10615544>

In the last section of this file, you will find a detailed description of the stored supplementary files. We welcome any collaboration and appreciate suggestions for developing new methodologies and investigating insect wings or other biological structures.

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1 Validation

Figure S1 displays the forewing of the Scarlet dragonfly. After extracting the junctions and cells of this wing using WingSegment, we employed our custom code (S1) to manually count them. The corresponding supplementary files for each panel are as follows:

- Panel b (Junctions Automated Detection): File S4
- Panel c (Cells Automated Detection): File S3
- Panel d (Junctions Manual Detection): File S2
- Panel e (Cells Manual Detection): File S1

Furthermore, Video S1 demonstrates the process of manually detecting cells, while Video S2 illustrates the manual detection of junctions.

Figure S1: Manual and automated detection of cells and junctions in the forewing of a Scarlet dragonfly. a) Scarlet dragonfly forewing. b) Automated detection of junctions using WingSegment. c) Automated detection of cells using WingSegment. d) Manual detection of junctions. e) Manual detection of cells.

2 Supplementary Codes

2.1 Code S1 (for validation): Manual Counting

Code S1 was developed for manually counting cells and junctions on insect wings, which was achieved through mouse clicking to mark cells and junctions. We employed this code to validate the automated cell and junction counting of WingSegment. The input for this code is the wing image, and the output consists of the coordinates of the marked cells and junctions.

Code S1: Custom code for manual marking of cells and junctions.

```
1 function Manual_Counter
2 [file,path,indx] = uigetfile('*.*.');
3 if indx
4     w = imread([path file]);
5 else
6     return
7 end
8 imshow(w)
9 prompt = {'What do you want to count?'};
10 dlgtitle = 'Input';
11 dims = [1 35];
12 definput = {''};
13 countingObject = inputdlg(prompt,dlgtitle,dims,definput);
14 e=1;
15 N = 0;
16 xAll=[]; yAll=[];
17 while e
18     [x,y]=getpts;
19     xAll=[xAll ; x];
20     yAll=[yAll ; y];
21     hold on
22     plot(x,y,'ro','markerfacecolor','r')
23     N = N+ size(x,1);
24     answer = questdlg('Would you like to continue counting?', ...
25         'Continue or Stop?',...
26         'Yes, please', 'No thank you','Yes, Please');
27     switch answer
28         case 'Yes, please'
29             disp([answer ' coming right up.'])
30             e = 1;
31         case 'No thank you'
32             disp([answer ' coming right up.'])
33             e = 0;
34     end
35 end
36 f = msgbox(['Number of ' countingObject{1} ': ' num2str(N)]);
37 writematrix([xAll yAll],[countingObject{1} ' Coordinates.csv'])
```

2.2 Code S2: Get Image

Code S2 is the function developed for importing the wing image. Line 1 in Code S2 defines the function.

Input: The input for this function is not explicitly defined. To import the wing image, we utilized the *uigetfile* function in MATLAB, allowing the user to import a desired file (in this case, the wing image). The output of *uigetfile* is the 'file' name and the 'path' where the file is stored.

Ouput: The outputs of this function is as follows:

- *imageBinaryImage*: This variable stores the binarized image of the wing.
- *imageOrgImage*: This variable stores the original matrix of the imported wing image.
- *imageWidth*: This variable stores the width of the imported image.
- *imageHeight*: This variable stores the height of the imported image.

Code Description: This code reads the image matrix in line 5. Line 6 checks whether the image is in RGB format. If the image is in RGB, the *rgb2gray* function in line 7 converts the image to grayscale. Line 9 is included to binarize the image using the *imbinarize* function. This function is a built-in MATLAB function that utilizes Otsu's method. The function requires a threshold value, and we have set it to 0.54 in this code. Lines 10 to 14 handle the cropping of the image to fit within a frame.

Code S2: GetImage code in MATLAB, for manual importing of the wing Image

```
1 function [imageBinaryImage ,imageOrgImage ,imageWidth ,imageHeight]=GetImage
2 [file,path,indx] = uigetfile( '*.*.');
3 ThresholdEditField = 0.54;
4 if indx
5     imageOrgImage = imread([path file]);
6     if size(imageOrgImage,3)==3
7         imageOrgImage = rgb2gray(imageOrgImage);
8     end
9     imageBinaryImage= imbinarize(imageOrgImage,ThresholdEditField); %Otsu's
    Method
10 [r,c] = find(imageBinaryImage==0);
11 imageBinaryImage = imageBinaryImage(min(min(r))-3:max(max(r))+3,min(min(c))
    -3:max(max(c))+3);
12 imageOrgImage = imageOrgImage(min(min(r))-3:max(max(r))+3,min(min(c))-3:max(
    max(c))+3);
13 imageWidth = size(imageOrgImage,2);
14 imageHeight = size(imageOrgImage,1);
15 end
16 end
```

2.3 Code S3: Region Growing

Region growing, as introduced in the main manuscript, extracts the boundary of a closed domain surrounded by black pixels.

Inputs: Three inputs are defined for Code S3:

- *imageBinaryImage*: The binary image, the first output of Code S2.
- *r*: The row number (y-coordinate) of a random seed inside a desired region.
- *c*: The column number (x-coordinate) of a random seed inside a desired region.

Outputs: Code S3 has four outputs:

- *cell_whiteID*: An N-by-2 array storing the coordinates of detected white pixels inside the desired region, used to generate the corresponding matrix for area, length, and circularity distribution of wing cells.
- *n_white*: The number of detected white pixels in the desired region, representing the area of the detected region.
- *im*: The image after detection of the region. When a desired region in the wing is detected, its color changes to gray to avoid repeated detection.
- *boundary*: An N-by-2 array containing the coordinates of the detected region.

Code Description:

- **line 3:** The binary image's matrix is converted to double because, upon importing an image into the function, the color of the detected area changes to gray, which is not possible in a binary image.
- **Line 4:** *FWP* represents 'Found White Pixels'. Initially, *r* and *c* (the second and third inputs of Code S3) go into *FWP*. This variable updates during the algorithm's execution.
- **Lines 5-6:** *border* and *cell_whiteID* are empty matrices that store the coordinates of detected boundary pixels and white pixels inside the region, respectively.
- **Lines 7-34:** The while loop starts from the initial seed point (*r*, *c*) and checks for new white (lines 8-18) and black pixels (lines 19-30) around the seed pixel. Each time it detects a new white or black pixel, it saves their coordinates separately. Also, each time it finds white pixels, it changes the color of those detected pixels and continues checking for new white pixels around those detected points. The while loop continues until there are still white pixels inside the region.
- **Lines 35-59:** In the while loop, detected pixels on the boundary are not in order. It means that the coordinates don't define a closed loop, and they are only points on the boundary that are stored irregularly. In lines 35-59, the code constructs a closed loop of those extracted points on the boundary of the domain.

To demonstrate how to run this function and use it for another project, we have developed Code S9. In this code, the user can simply import a desired image and click inside one region, and the code extracts that region's boundary.

Code S3: Region Growing Code in MATLAB

```
1 function [cell_whiteID,n_white,im,boundary]= RegionGrowing(imageBinaryImage,r,c)
2 %r, and c represent the row and column number of a random seed inside the desired
   region
3 im = double(imageBinaryImage);
4 FWP=[c,r];          % FWP:found white pixel(first white pixel is choosen by user)
5 border=[];
6 cell_whiteID=[];
7 while ~isempty(FWP) %the code continues while it does not find new white pixe
8     X=[FWP(:,1) FWP(:,1)      FWP(:,1)+1      FWP(:,1)      FWP(:,1)-1];
9     Y=[FWP(:,2) FWP(:,2)-1      FWP(:,2)      FWP(:,2)+1      FWP(:,2)];
10    X=X(:); Y=Y(:);
11    l=length(X);
12    new_FWP=[];
13    for i=1:l
14        if im(Y(i),X(i))==1
```

```

15         im(Y(i),X(i))=0.8; % changes the color of found white pixel to bright
16             grey
17         new_FWP=[new_FWP; X(i) Y(i)];    %#ok %new_FWP: new Found White Pixel
18     end
19     % Finding new black pixels in the neighbor of FWP on 8 directions
20     X=[FWP(:,1) FWP(:,1)+1 FWP(:,1) FWP(:,1)-1 FWP(:,1)-1 FWP(:,1)-1 FWP(:,1)+1
21         FWP(:,1)+1];
22     Y=[FWP(:,2)-1 FWP(:,2) FWP(:,2)+1 FWP(:,2) FWP(:,2)-1 FWP(:,2)+1 FWP(:,2)-1
23         FWP(:,2)+1];
24     X=X(:); Y=Y(:);
25     l=length(X);
26     new_FBP=[];
27     for i=1:l
28         if im(Y(i),X(i))==0
29             im(Y(i),X(i))=0.1; % changes the color of found black pixel to dark
30                 grey
31             new_FBP=[new_FBP; X(i) Y(i)];    %#ok %new_FBP: new Found Black Pixel
32         end
33         border=[border;new_FBP];                %#ok
34         cell_whiteID=[cell_whiteID;new_FWP];    %#ok
35         FWP=new_FWP;
36     end
37     border = unique(border, 'rows');
38     n_white=size(unique(cell_whiteID, 'rows'),1);
39     im_bw = zeros(size(im,1),size(im,2));
40     for i=1:size(border,1)
41         im_bw(border(i,2),border(i,1))=1;
42         im(border(i,2),border(i,1))=0;
43     end
44     BW = imbinarize(im_bw);
45     try
46         boundary = bwtraceboundary(BW , [border(i,2),border(i,1)], 'S');
47     catch
48         try
49             boundary = bwtraceboundary(BW , [border(i,2),border(i,1)], 'E');
50         catch
51             try
52                 boundary = bwtraceboundary(BW , [border(i,2),border(i,1)], 'N');
53             catch
54                 boundary = bwtraceboundary(BW , [border(i,2),border(i,1)], 'W');
55             end
56         end
57     end
58     boundary = [boundary(:,2) boundary(:,1)];
59     boundary(:,2)=size(im,1)-boundary(:,2);
60     [boundary(:,1), boundary(:,2)] = poly2cw(boundary(:,1), boundary(:,2));
61     im = double(im);
62 end

```

2.4 Code S4: Wing Cell Segmentation

This code is developed to segment all cells of a wing by repeatedly applying the *RegionGrowing* function.

Input: The only input of this function is the binary image generated by the *GetImage* function.

Outputs: Code S4 has six outputs as follows:

- *ContourMatrix_Area*: Stores the matrix generated by *RegionGrowing* that contains the corresponding matrix for the distribution of wing cells' areas.
- *ContourMatrix_Length*: Similar to the previous one, this variable contains the distribution of wing cells' lengths.
- *ContourMatrix_Circularity*: This variable similarly contains the distribution of wing cells' circularities.
- *wingOutline*: This is an N-by-2 array that contains the coordinates of the wing outline, extracted from *RegionGrowing*.
- *wingCells*: This is a one-by-N cell array. The number of cells in this array represents the number of wing cells, and each cell array contains the coordinates of one wing cell boundary.
- *wingInfo*: This is an N-by-6 matrix. N represents the number of cells. Each row of this variable has six columns representing the cell index, the x-coordinate of the cell centroid, the y-coordinate of the cell centroid, the cell's area, the cell's length, and the cell's circularity.

Code Description:

- **Lines 8-11:** These lines generate a gray frame around the image. This is necessary for extracting the outline of the wing. Otherwise, the *RegionGrowing* function faces problems when it reaches the edge of the image (first and last columns and rows of the image matrix).
- **Line 16:** *RegionGrowing* runs in this line to extract the outline of the wing.
- **Lines 32-63:** In line 32, a *while* loop starts. In this while loop, the *RegionGrowing* function runs recursively until all cells are detected. As mentioned, the second and third inputs of the *RegionGrowing* function are one seed point inside the region. Keep in mind that the outline is already detected, and as a result, the color of the outer region of the wing image is already gray. To find the first seed inside the first cell, in line 30 the code finds all white pixels, and in line 33, it uses only the first detected white pixel. As the outer region of the wing is gray, this white pixel is located inside one of the cells. Then, *RegionGrowing* extracts that specific cell's boundary and changes the color of that cell to gray. Then inside the loop in line 60, the code again searches for new white pixels, and absolutely these white pixels are inside not detected cells because all detected cells have changed color to gray. This while loop continues until the code finds no new white pixels. Video S3 in the supplementary materials visually demonstrates this procedure.

Code S4: Wing Cells Segmentation Code in MATLAB

```
1 function [ContourMatrix_Area,...
2     ContourMatrix_Length,...
3     ContourMatrix_Circularity,...
4     wingOutline,...
5     wingCells,...
6     wingInfo] = cellSegment(imageBinaryImage)
7 w = double(imageBinaryImage);
8 w(1,:)=.5;
9 w(end,:)=.5;
10 w(:,1)=.5;
11 w(:,end)=0.5;
12 s_im=size(w);
13 r=2; c=2;
14 wingInfo = [];
15 wingCells ={};
16 [cell_whiteID,~,w,boundary]=RegionGrowing(w,c,r);
17 wingOutline= boundary;
18 ContourMatrix_Area=zeros(s_im(1),s_im(2));
```

```

19 for i=1:size(cell_whiteID,1)
20     ContourMatrix_Area(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1))=NaN;
21 end
22 ContourMatrix_Length=zeros(s_im(1),s_im(2));
23 for i=1:size(cell_whiteID,1)
24     ContourMatrix_Length(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1))=NaN;
25 end
26 ContourMatrix_Circularity=zeros(s_im(1),s_im(2));
27 for i=1:size(cell_whiteID,1)
28     ContourMatrix_Circularity(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1))=NaN;
29 end
30 [r,c]=find(w==1);
31 count=0;
32 allDetected = 0;
33 while sum(r)>0     [cell_whiteID,n_white,w,boundary]=RegionGrowing(w,r(1),c(1));
34     if n_white > 8
35         wingCells{end+1}= boundary;
36         count=count+1;
37         s_b=size(boundary,1);
38         all_l=[];
39         for i=1:s_b
40             l=sqrt(((boundary(i,1)-boundary(:,1)).^2)+(boundary(i,2)-boundary
41                 (:,2)).^2);
42             all_l=[all_l;l];    %#ok
43         end
44         all_ll = [];
45         for i=1:size(boundary,1)-1
46             ll=sqrt(((boundary(i,1)-boundary(i+1,1)).^2)+(boundary(i,2)-boundary(
47                 i+1,2)).^2);
48             all_ll=[all_ll;ll];    %#ok
49         end
50         Perimeter = sum(all_ll);
51         Rc = Perimeter/(2*pi);
52         for i=1:size(cell_whiteID,1)
53             if ~isempty(all_l)
54                 ContourMatrix_Area(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1))=n_white;
55                 ContourMatrix_Length(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1))=max(
56                     all_l);
57                 ContourMatrix_Circularity(cell_whiteID(i,2),cell_whiteID(i,1)) =
58                     n_white/(pi*(Rc^2));
59             end
60         end
61         wingInfo(count,:) = [count...
62             mean(boundary(:,1))...
63             mean(boundary(:,2))...
64             n_white...
65             max(all_l)...
66             n_white/(pi*(Rc^2))];
67     end
68     [r,c]=find(w==1);
69     id_gray = w==0.1;
70     w(id_gray) = 0;
71 end
72 id = ContourMatrix_Area == 0;
73 ContourMatrix_Area(id) = nan;
74 ContourMatrix_Area = ContourMatrix_Area(end:-1:1,:);
75 id= ContourMatrix_Length == 0;

```

```
72 ContourMatrix_Length(id) = nan;
73 ContourMatrix_Length = ContourMatrix_Length(end:-1:1,:);
74 id= ContourMatrix_Circularity == 0;
75 ContourMatrix_Circularity(id) = nan;
76 ContourMatrix_Circularity = ContourMatrix_Circularity(end:-1:1,:);
77 end
```

2.5 Code S5: Junction Detection/Skeletonization

This function is developed to detect junctions of the wing.

Input: The only input for this function is the binary image of the wing.

Outputs: This function has two outputs:

- *junctions*: A structure variable with the following fields:
 - *junctions.c*: An N-by-1 array storing the X coordinate of junctions.
 - *junctions.r*: An N-by-1 array storing the Y coordinate of junctions.
 - *junctions.surround.x*: An N-by-20 array containing the X coordinate of a circle with a radius of 1.5 pixels around junctions (used in the detection of veins).
 - *junctions.surround.y*: An N-by-20 array containing the Y coordinate of a circle with a radius of 1.5 pixels around junctions (used in the detection of veins).

N in this array represents the number of detected junctions.

- *skeletonizedImage*: A matrix representing the skeletonized image of the wing.

Code Description:

- **Lines 5-11:** These lines apply the distance transform on the wing image. This feature can be turned on or off by setting the value of the *Distancetransform* variable to 1 or 0. Distance transform can detect the location of the Pterostigma in the wing.
- **Line 14:** Applies the thinning method to generate the skeletonized image.
- **Lines 17-40:** Implements the conditions used to detect the locations of junctions.
- **Lines 44-52:** Modifies detected junctions to remove junctions located within a distance of less than 3 pixels from each other.

Code S5: Junction Detection code in MATLAB, for automated Wing Junction Detection

```
1 function [junctions, skeletonizedImage]=junctionDetection(imageBinaryImage)
2 wOrg = imageBinaryImage;
3 w = imageBinaryImage;
4 Distancetransform = 0; %This value can be 0 or 1
5 if Distancetransform
6     w = bwdist(w);
7     w = w/max(max(w));
8     w(w>0.7) =1;
9     w(w<=0.7) = 0;
10    w=wOrg + w;
11 end
12 w=~w;
13 w = double(w);
14 w = bwmorph(w, 'thin',100);
15 w = double(w);
16 skeletonizedImage = ~w;
17 w1 = w(2:end-1,2:end-1);
18 w2 = w(1:end-2,2:end-1);
19 w3 = w(1:end-2,3:end);
20 w4 = w(2:end-1,3:end);
21 w5 = w(3:end,3:end);
22 w6 = w(3:end,2:end-1);
23 w7 = w(3:end,1:end-2);
24 w8 = w(2:end-1,1:end-2);
25 w9 = w(1:end-2,1:end-2);
26 id1 = w1+w2+w4+w6+w8==4 & w1==1;
27 id2 = w1+w2+w4+w6+w8==5 & w1==1;
```

```

28 id3 =(w1+w2+w4+w7)==4 & w1==1;
29 id4 = (w1+w4+w6+w9)==4 & w1==1;
30 id5 = (w1+w6+w8+w3)==4 & w1==1;
31 id6 = (w1+w2+w8+w5)==4 & w1==1;
32 id7 = (w1+w3+w5+w8-w4)==4 & w1==1;
33 id8 = (w1+w5+w7+w2-w6)==4 & w1==1;
34 id9 = (w1+w7+w9+w4-w8)==4 & w1==1;
35 id10 = (w1+w9+w3+w6-w2)==4 & w1==1;
36 id11 = (w1+w3+w5+w7+w9)==4 & w1==1;
37 id12 = (w1+w3+w5+w7+w9)==5 & w1==1;
38 id13 = w2+w3+w4+w5+w6+w7+w8+w9==1 & w1==1;
39 id = id1+id2+id3+id4+id5+id6+id7+id8+id9+id10+id11+id12+id13;
40 [r,c] = find(id>=1);
41 r=r+1;
42 c=c+1;
43 finalJoints=[];
44 while ~isempty(r)
45     rCP = r(1);
46     cCP = c(1);
47     d = sqrt((r-rCP).^2+(c-cCP).^2);
48     id = d<=3;
49     finalJoints = [finalJoints; mean(r(id)) mean(c(id))];    %#ok
50     r(id)=[];
51     c(id)=[];
52 end
53 finalJoints = round(unique(finalJoints,'rows'));
54 junctions.c = finalJoints(:,2);
55 junctions.r = finalJoints(:,1);
56 t = linspace(0,2*pi,20);
57 x = 1.5*cos(t);
58 y = 1.5*sin(t);
59 junctions.surround.x = zeros(length(junctions.c),20);
60 junctions.surround.y = zeros(length(junctions.r),20);
61 for i = 1 : length(junctions.c)
62     junctions.surround.x(i,:)= x+ junctions.c(i);
63     junctions.surround.y(i,:) = y+ junctions.r(i);
64 end
65 end

```

2.6 Code S6: Parallel Vein Detection (PVD)

This function detects the venation pattern inside the wing using the parallel method introduced in the manuscript.

Inputs: This function has two inputs. Both inputs are generated by the *junctionDetection* function (Code S5). These inputs are as follows:

- *skeletonizedImage*
- *junctions*

Outputs: This function has one output as follows:

- *detectedVeins*: This variable is a structure with the following fields:
 - *detectedVeins.coordinate*: A 1-by-N cell array. N represents the number of detected veins. Each cell of this array contains the coordinate of the vein path.
 - *detectedVeins.length*: A 1-by-N array storing the length of veins. This variable is used in plotting a histogram.
 - *detectedVeins.Color*: An N-by-3 matrix that stores the corresponding color of each vein considering the vein length. These colors are used to plot a heatmap of the venation pattern.

Code Description:

- **Lines 7-16:** This code is a modified path-finding method that is adopted to detect the path between junctions (venation pattern). The initial point for starting finding a path is the junctions that are detected in Code S5. Lines 7 and 8 show these initial points. Each initial point detects new points on the path. In this code, only venations are white (pixel value = 1), and the rest are black (pixel value = 0). This code defines a variable named *front*. This variable stores the data related to the new points detected on the venation path. This variable is a structure with the following fields:
 - *front.Index*: Stores the index of front points. We used this variable to change the color of front points easily (Line 10). This avoids the code from checking already detected points on the path.
 - *front.c*: Stores the column index (x coordinate) of front points.
 - *front.r*: Stores the row index (y coordinate) of front points.
 - *front.parent*: Each new detected point on the path of the vein should know its origin (parent). In this case, when the path starts to be detected from one joint and it reaches another junction, which means that the path is already detected, the very last front point that meets a new junction finds its way back from its parents until it reaches the initial point. This means the path between those junctions is extracted. This variable has also two fields as follows.
 - * *front.parent.c*: The column index (x coordinate) of the parent of the front points.
 - * *front.parent.r*: The row index (y coordinate) of the parent of the front points.
- **Lines 17-93:** Line 17 starts a while loop in which the initial point from all junctions parallelly starts finding their path on the skeletonized image of the wing. In lines 18-35, the front points are defined. In lines 36-39, their parents are defined. In lines 41-48, all repetitive front points are removed. In lines 49-70, all front points that are not on the path (out of the path in the black area or in the area of the detected path, which is gray) are removed. In lines 70-92, the code checks if fronts from different paths meet each other or not. This while loop continues until no white pixels are inside the wing. Video S4 in the supplementary material visualizes this process.
- **Lines 117-156:** After all fronts meet each other (technically in the middle of each vein), another while loop extracts the venation pattern. In this case, each vein is divided into two halves. The direction of points on these two halves is opposite. Then the first half extracts in lines 108-125. Then the second half extracts in lines 126-143. Then, in lines 144-55, the second half reverses and merges with the first half, and also the length of veins is measured in lines 149-154.
- **Lines 157-162:** In these lines, the code finds the color of each vein corresponding to its length from the jet colormap.

Code S6: Parallel Vein Detection code in MATLAB, for automated vein detecting using parallel detection method

```

1 function detectedVeins = veinDetection_PVD(skeletonizedImage , junctions)
2 w = double(~skeletonizedImage);
3 joints = junctions;
4 image.width = size(w,2);
5 image.height = size(w,1);
6 %%
7 initialPoint.c = joints.c';
8 initialPoint.r = joints.r';
9 front.Index = ((initialPoint.c-1)*image.height)+initialPoint.r;
10 w(front.Index) = 0.3;
11 detectedPoints.c = initialPoint.c;
12 detectedPoints.r = initialPoint.r;
13 detectedPoints.parent.c = zeros(1,length(initialPoint.c));
14 detectedPoints.parent.r = zeros(1,length(initialPoint.c));
15 meetingPoints.main = [];
16 meetingPoints.parent = [];
17 while any(any(w==1)) && ~isempty( initialPoint.c)
18     front.c = [...
19         initialPoint.c+1,...           %Column Index: Right Pixel
20         initialPoint.c+1,...           %Column Index: UpRight Pixel
21         initialPoint.c,...             %Column Index: Up Pixel
22         initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: UpLeft Pixel
23         initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: Left Pixel
24         initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: LeftBottom Pixel
25         initialPoint.c,...             %Column Index: Bottom Pixel
26         initialPoint.c+1];             %Column Index: BottomRight Pixel
27     front.r = [...
28         initialPoint.r,...             %Column Index: Right Pixel
29         initialPoint.r-1,...           %Column Index: UpRight Pixel
30         initialPoint.r-1,...           %Column Index: Up Pixel
31         initialPoint.r-1,...           %Column Index: UpLeft Pixel
32         initialPoint.r,...             %Column Index: Left Pixel
33         initialPoint.r+1,...           %Column Index: LeftBottom Pixel
34         initialPoint.r+1,...           %Column Index: Bottom Pixel
35         initialPoint.r+1];             %Column Index: BottomRight Pixel
36     front.parent.c = repmat(initialPoint.c,1,8);
37     front.parent.c = front.parent.c(:)';
38     front.parent.r = repmat(initialPoint.r,1,8);
39     front.parent.r = front.parent.r(:)';
40     front.Index = ((front.c-1)*image.height)+front.r;
41     %% Unique front
42     Front = [front.c' front.r' front.parent.c' front.parent.r'];
43     [~,iUnique,~] = unique(Front,'rows');
44     front.c = front.c(iUnique);
45     front.r = front.r(iUnique);
46     front.parent.c = front.parent.c(iUnique);
47     front.parent.r = front.parent.r(iUnique);
48     front.Index = front.Index(iUnique);
49     %% Remove out of bound nodes of the front
50     id1_outOfBount = front.Index < 1;
51     id2_outOfBount = front.Index > numel(w);
52     front.c (id1_outOfBount) = [];
53     front.r (id1_outOfBount) = [];
54     front.parent.c(id1_outOfBount) = [];
55     front.parent.r(id1_outOfBount) = [];
56     front.Index (id1_outOfBount) = [];

```

```

57     front.c (id2_outOfBount) = [];
58     front.r (id2_outOfBount) = [];
59     front.parent.c(id2_outOfBount) = [];
60     front.parent.r(id2_outOfBount) = [];
61     front.Index (id2_outOfBount) = [];
62     %% Remove black/gray pixels of the front
63     id_black =w(front.Index) ~= 1;
64     front.c (id_black) = [];
65     front.r (id_black) = [];
66     front.parent.c(id_black) = [];
67     front.parent.r(id_black) = [];
68     front.Index (id_black) = [];
69     w(front.Index) = 0.3;
70     %%
71     detectedPoints.c = [detectedPoints.c     front.c];
72     detectedPoints.r = [detectedPoints.r     front.r];
73     detectedPoints.parent.c = [detectedPoints.parent.c     front.parent.c];
74     detectedPoints.parent.r = [detectedPoints.parent.r     front.parent.r];
75     %%
76     [x,y] = meshgrid(1:length(front.c));
77     X = x(x~=y);
78     Y = y(x~=y);
79     d1= sqrt(((front.c(X(:))-front.c(Y(:))).^2) + ((front.r(X(:))-front.r(Y(:)))
      .^2))');
80     d2= sqrt(((front.parent.c(X(:))-front.parent.c(Y(:))).^2) + ((front.parent.r(
      X(:))-front.parent.r(Y(:))).^2))');
81     id = find (d1 <1.5 & d2>1.5);
82     if ~isempty(id)
83         for i = 1:length(id)
84             meetingPoints.main(end+1,1:4) = [front.c(X(id(i)))     front.r(X(id(
              i)))     front.c(Y(id(i)))     front.r(Y(id(i)))];
85             meetingPoints.parent(end+1,1:4) = [front.parent.c(X(id(i)))
              front.parent.r(X(id(i)))     front.parent.c(Y(id(i)))
              front.parent.r(Y(id(i)))];
86         end
87         id_Siblings = find((meetingPoints.parent(:,1) == meetingPoints.parent
              (:,3)) & (meetingPoints.parent(:,2) == meetingPoints.parent(:,4)));
88         meetingPoints.parent(id_Siblings,:) = [];
89         meetingPoints.main(id_Siblings,:) = [];
90     end
91     initialPoint.c = front.c;
92     initialPoint.r = front.r;
93 end
94 id_Siblings = (meetingPoints.parent(:,1) == meetingPoints.parent(:,3)) & (
      meetingPoints.parent(:,2) == meetingPoints.parent(:,4));
95 meetingPoints.parent(id_Siblings,:) = [];
96 meetingPoints.main(id_Siblings,:) = [];
97 [meetingPoints.main,id,~] = unique(meetingPoints.main, 'rows');
98 meetingPoints.parent = meetingPoints.parent(id,:);
99 s1 = [mean(meetingPoints.main(:, [1 3]),2)     mean(meetingPoints.main(:, [2 4]),2)
      ];
100 s2 = [mean(meetingPoints.parent(:, [1 3]),2)     mean(meetingPoints.parent(:, [2 4])
      ,2)];
101 d = sqrt(sum((s1'-s2').^2));
102 meetingPoints.main = meetingPoints.main(d<=0.5,:);
103 meetingPoints.parent = meetingPoints.parent(d<=0.5,:);
104 MeetingPoints_backUp = meetingPoints.main;

```

```

105 detectedVeins.coordinate = {};
106 detectedVeins.length = [];
107 while ~isempty(MeetingPoints_backUp)
108     %% FirstHalf
109     id = find(detectedPoints.c==MeetingPoints_backUp(1,1) & detectedPoints.r==
        MeetingPoints_backUp(1,2),1);
110     path1.c = [detectedPoints.c(id) detectedPoints.parent.c(id)];
111     path1.r = [detectedPoints.r(id) detectedPoints.parent.r(id)];
112     detectedPoints.c(id) = [];
113     detectedPoints.r(id) = [];
114     detectedPoints.parent.c(id) = [];
115     detectedPoints.parent.r(id) = [];
116     isDetected = false;
117     while ~isDetected && ~isempty(path1.c) && ~isempty(id)
118         id = find(detectedPoints.c==path1.c(end) & detectedPoints.r==path1.r(end)
            ,1);
119         if detectedPoints.parent.c(id)==0
120             isDetected = true;
121         elseif ~isempty(id)
122             path1.c(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.c(id);
123             path1.r(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.r(id);
124         end
125     end
126     %% SecondHalf
127     id = find(detectedPoints.c==MeetingPoints_backUp(1,3) & detectedPoints.r==
        MeetingPoints_backUp(1,4),1);
128     path2.c = [detectedPoints.c(id) detectedPoints.parent.c(id)];
129     path2.r = [detectedPoints.r(id) detectedPoints.parent.r(id)];
130     detectedPoints.c(id) = [];
131     detectedPoints.r(id) = [];
132     detectedPoints.parent.c(id) = [];
133     detectedPoints.parent.r(id) = [];
134     isDetected = false;
135     while ~isDetected && ~isempty(path2.c) && ~isempty(id)
136         id = find(detectedPoints.c==path2.c(end) & detectedPoints.r==path2.r(end)
            ,1);
137         if detectedPoints.parent.c(id)==0
138             isDetected = true;
139         elseif ~isempty(id)
140             path2.c(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.c(id);
141             path2.r(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.r(id);
142         end
143     end
144     %% MergeHalf
145     detectedPath = [...
146         path1.c(end:-1:1) path2.c;...
147         path1.r(end:-1:1) path2.r];
148     detectedPath = unique(detectedPath','rows','stable');
149     if ~isempty(detectedPath)
150         [latout,lonout] = reducem(detectedPath(1,:)','detectedPath(2,:)','1.5);
151         detectedVeins.coordinate(end+1) = {[latout lonout]};
152         d = sqrt(((latout(2:end)-latout(1:end-1)).^2)+((lonout(2:end)-lonout(1:
            end-1)).^2));
153         detectedVeins.length(end+1) = sum(d);
154     end
155     MeetingPoints_backUp(1,:) = [];
156 end

```

```
157 Data = detectedVeins.length;
158 maxData = max(max(detectedVeins.length));
159 minData = min(min(detectedVeins.length));
160 colorMap = jet;
161 idColor = round(1+(((Data-minData)/(maxData-minData))*255));
162 detectedVeins.Color = colorMap(idColor,:);
163 end
```

2.7 Code S7: Sequential Vein Detection (SVD)

Code S7 is the code that detects junctions using the sequential method. The inputs and outputs of this function are similar to those in Code S6.

Code Description: Some parts of this code are different from PVD; as a result, we only describe where necessary.

- **Line 9:** This line starts a *while* loop, which refers to the junctions. This loop lets the code continue its work until all junctions are involved in the process of vein detection. In this method, in contrast to the PVD method, in each step, only one junction searches all paths that are connected to that junction until it reaches other junctions. This loop continues until all junctions are involved.
- **Line 26:** This line starts another *while* loop which is located inside the previous loop. This loop relates to the individual junction, which is searching connected paths. This while loop continues until all paths connected to that individual junction are checked.
- **Lines 71-100:** These lines in each step check if the front points meet another junction or not. It should be mentioned that normally, several veins are connected to each junction. This means each junction is checking several paths at the same time to find other new junctions. Video S5 in the supplementary information visualizes this process.
- **Lines 132-156:** When one individual junction has detected all connected junctions, this *for* loop finds the path between those junctions by tracking their parents.

Code S7: Sequential Vein Detection (SVD) code in MATLAB, for automated vein detecting using parallel detection method

```
1 function detectedVeins = veinDetection_SVD(skeletonizedImage, junctions)
2 joints = junctions;
3 w = double(~skeletonizedImage);
4 image.width = size(w,2);
5 image.height = size(w,1);
6 detectedVeins = {};
7 detectedVeins.coordinate = {};
8 detectedVeins.length = [];
9 while ~isempty(joints.c)
10     initialPoint.c = joints.c(1);
11     initialPoint.r = joints.r(1);
12     endingPoint.c = [];
13     endingPoint.r = [];
14     endingPoint.parent.r = [];
15     endingPoint.parent.c = [];
16     w(initialPoint.r,initialPoint.c) = 0.3;
17     joints.c(1,:) = [];
18     joints.r(1,:) = [];
19     joints.surround.x(1,:) = [];
20     joints.surround.y(1,:) = [];
21     detectedPoints.c = initialPoint.c;
22     detectedPoints.r = initialPoint.r;
23     detectedPoints.parent.c = 0;
24     detectedPoints.parent.r = 0;
25     isDetected = false;
26     while ~isDetected
27         %% Define front pixels
28         front.c = [...
29             initialPoint.c+1,...           %Column Index: Right Pixel
30             initialPoint.c+1,...           %Column Index: UpRight Pixel
31             initialPoint.c,...             %Column Index: Up Pixel
32             initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: UpLeft Pixel
33             initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: Left Pixel
34             initialPoint.c-1,...           %Column Index: LeftBottom Pixel
```

```

35     initialPoint.c,...           %Column Index: Bottom Pixel
36     initialPoint.c+1];         %Column Index: BottomRight Pixel
37 front.r = [...
38     initialPoint.r,...           %Column Index: Right Pixel
39     initialPoint.r-1,...         %Column Index: UpRight Pixel
40     initialPoint.r-1,...         %Column Index: Up Pixel
41     initialPoint.r-1,...         %Column Index: UpLeft Pixel
42     initialPoint.r,...           %Column Index: Left Pixel
43     initialPoint.r+1,...         %Column Index: LeftBottom Pixel
44     initialPoint.r+1,...         %Column Index: Bottom Pixel
45     initialPoint.r+1];         %Column Index: BottomRight Pixel
46 front.parent.c = repmat(initialPoint.c,1,8);
47 front.parent.c = front.parent.c(:)';
48 front.parent.r = repmat(initialPoint.r,1,8);
49 front.parent.r = front.parent.r(:)';
50 front.Index = ((front.c-1)*image.height)+front.r;
51 %% Remove out of bound nodes of the front
52 id1_outOfBount = front.Index < 1;
53 id2_outOfBount = front.Index > numel(w);
54 front.c (id1_outOfBount) = [];
55 front.r (id1_outOfBount) = [];
56 front.parent.c(id1_outOfBount) = [];
57 front.parent.r(id1_outOfBount) = [];
58 front.Index (id1_outOfBount) = [];
59 front.c (id2_outOfBount) = [];
60 front.r (id2_outOfBount) = [];
61 front.parent.c(id2_outOfBount) = [];
62 front.parent.r(id2_outOfBount) = [];
63 front.Index (id2_outOfBount) = [];
64 %% Remove gray pixels of the front
65 id_notWhite =w(front.Index) ~= 1;
66 front.c (id_notWhite) = [];
67 front.r (id_notWhite) = [];
68 front.parent.c(id_notWhite) = [];
69 front.parent.r(id_notWhite) = [];
70 front.Index (id_notWhite) = [];
71 %% Check if front is in junction area
72 for iJunctions = 1 : length(joints.c)
73     xv = joints.surround.x(iJunctions,:);
74     yv = joints.surround.y(iJunctions,:);
75     xq.c = front.c;
76     yq.r = front.r;
77     xq.parent = front.parent.c;
78     yq.parent = front.parent.r;
79     removeFront = [];
80     for iFront = 1 : length(xq.c)
81         in = inpolygon(xq.c(iFront),yq.r(iFront),xv,yv);
82         % Save detected points if are inside junction area
83         if any(in)
84             detectedPoints.c =[detectedPoints.c     xq.c(iFront)
85                               joints.c(iJunctions)];
86             detectedPoints.r = [detectedPoints.r     yq.r(iFront)
87                               joints.r(iJunctions)]; %*ones(1,sum(in))
88             detectedPoints.parent.c = [detectedPoints.parent.c     xq.parent
89                                       (iFront)     xq.c(iFront) ];
89             detectedPoints.parent.r = [detectedPoints.parent.r     yq.
90                                       parent(iFront)     yq.r(iFront) ];

```

```

88         removeFront = [removeFront iFront]; %#ok
89         endingPoint.c = [endingPoint.c      joints.c(iJunctions)];
90         endingPoint.r = [endingPoint.r      joints.r(iJunctions)];
91         endingPoint.parent.c = [endingPoint.parent.c      xq.parent(
92             iFront)];
93         endingPoint.parent.r = [endingPoint.parent.r      yq.parent(
94             iFront)];
95     end
96 end
97 front.c(removeFront) = [];
98 front.r(removeFront) = [];
99 front.parent.c(removeFront) = [];
100 front.parent.r(removeFront) = [];
101 front.Index(removeFront) = [];
102 end
103 %% Save detected points
104 detectedPoints.c=[detectedPoints.c front.c ];
105 detectedPoints.r = [detectedPoints.r front.r ];
106 detectedPoints.parent.c = [detectedPoints.parent.c front.parent.c];
107 detectedPoints.parent.r = [detectedPoints.parent.r front.parent.r];
108 if isempty(front.c)
109     isDetected = true;
110 end
111 w(front.Index) = 0.3;
112 initialPoint.c = front.c;
113 initialPoint.r = front.r;
114 end
115 if ~isempty(endingPoint.c)
116     allEnding = [
117         endingPoint.c
118         endingPoint.r
119         endingPoint.parent.c
120         endingPoint.parent.r];
121     ckeckEnding = unique(allEnding','rows');
122     endingPoint.c = ckeckEnding(:,1)';
123     endingPoint.r = ckeckEnding(:,2)';
124     allDetectedPoints = [
125         detectedPoints.c
126         detectedPoints.r
127         detectedPoints.parent.c
128         detectedPoints.parent.r];
129     ckeckDetected = unique(allDetectedPoints','rows');
130     detectedPoints.c = ckeckDetected(:,1)';
131     detectedPoints.r = ckeckDetected(:,2)';
132     detectedPoints.parent.c = ckeckDetected(:,3)';
133     detectedPoints.parent.r = ckeckDetected(:,4)';
134     for i= 1: length(endingPoint.c)
135         id = find(detectedPoints.c==endingPoint.c(i) & detectedPoints.r ==
136             endingPoint.r(i),1);
137         path.c = [detectedPoints.c(id) detectedPoints.parent.c(id)];
138         path.r = [detectedPoints.r(id) detectedPoints.parent.r(id)];
139         detectedPoints.c(id) = [];
140         detectedPoints.r(id) = [];
141         detectedPoints.parent.c(id) = [];
142         detectedPoints.parent.r(id) = [];
143         isDetected = false;
144         while ~isDetected && ~isempty(path.c)

```

```

142         id = find(detectedPoints.c==path.c(end) & detectedPoints.r ==
143             path.r(end),1);
144         if detectedPoints.parent.c(id)==0
145             isDetected = true;
146         else
147             path.c(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.c(id);
148             path.r(end+1) = detectedPoints.parent.r(id);
149         end
150     end
151     if ~isempty(path.c)
152         [latout,lonout] = reducem(path.c',path.r',1);
153         detectedVeins.coordinate(end+1) = {[latout lonout]};
154         d = sqrt(((latout(2:end)-latout(1:end-1)).^2)+((lonout(2:end)-
155             lonout(1:end-1)).^2));
156         detectedVeins.length(end+1) = sum(d);
157     end
158 end
159 Data = detectedVeins.length;
160 maxData = max(max(detectedVeins.length));
161 minData = min(min(detectedVeins.length));
162 colorMap = jet;
163 idColor = round(1+(((Data-minData)/(maxData-minData))*255));
164 detectedVeins.Color = colorMap(idColor,:);
165 end

```

2.8 Code S8: FreeCAD Macro File Generation

This function is developed to generate a FreeCAD macro file.

Inputs: This function has two inputs as follows:

- *wingOutline*: This variable is exactly the 4th output of Code S4.
- *wingCells*: This variable is exactly the 5th output of Code S4.

Output: The only output of this function is an FCMacro file.

Code Description:

- **Lines 22-24:** This loop defines the wing outline.
- **Lines 31-42:** These loops define the wing cell domains.

Code S8: FreeCAD Macro File Generation code in MATLAB

```
1 function generateFreeCadModel(wingOutline,wingCells)
2 [file,path] = uiputfile('*.FCMacro');
3 fid = fopen([path file],'w');
4 fprintf(fid,'import FreeCAD\n');
5 fprintf(fid,'import Draft\n');
6 fprintf(fid,'App.newDocument("Wing")\n');
7 fprintf(fid,'def makewire(Name,PointList,Placement= False,Closed=False,Support=
    None,Face=None):\n');
8 fprintf(fid,'    WireObj = FreeCAD.ActiveDocument.addObject("Part::
    Part2DObjectPython",Name)\n');
9 fprintf(fid,'    Draft._Wire(WireObj)\n');
10 fprintf(fid,'    WireObj.Points = PointList\n');
11 fprintf(fid,'    WireObj.Closed = Closed\n');
12 fprintf(fid,'    WireObj.Support = Support\n');
13 fprintf(fid,'    if Face != None:\n');
14 fprintf(fid,'        WireObj.MakeFace = Face\n');
15 fprintf(fid,'    if Placement: WireObj.Placement = Placement\n');
16 fprintf(fid,'    if Gui:\n');
17 fprintf(fid,'        Draft._ViewProviderWire(WireObj.ViewObject)\n');
18 fprintf(fid,'        Draft.formatObject(WireObj)\n');
19 fprintf(fid,'        Draft.select(WireObj)\n');
20 fprintf(fid,'    FreeCAD.ActiveDocument.recompute()\n');
21 fprintf(fid,'points=[\n');
22 for i = 1: length(wingOutline)
23     fprintf(fid,'FreeCAD.Vector(%g,%g,0.0),\n',wingOutline(i,1),wingOutline(i,2))
24     ;
25 end
26 fprintf(fid,'    ]\n');
27 fprintf(fid,'Pl = App.Placement(Pos =(0,0,0))\n');
28 fprintf(fid,'Pl.Rotation.Q = (0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0)\n');
29 fprintf(fid,'Pl.Base = points[0]\n');
30 fprintf(fid,'makewire("Outline", points,Placement= Pl)\n');
31 fprintf(fid,'FreeCAD.getDocument(''Wing'').getObject(''Outline'').Placement = App
    .Placement(App.Vector(0.00,0.00,0.00),App.Rotation(App.Vector(0.00,0.00,1.00)
    ,0.00))\n');
32 for j = 1 : length(wingCells)
33     fprintf(fid,'points=[\n');
34     for i = 1: length(wingCells{j})
35         fprintf(fid,'FreeCAD.Vector(%g,%g,0.0),\n',wingCells{j}(i,1),wingCells{j}
36             }(i,2));
37     end
38     fprintf(fid,'    ]\n');
```

```
37     fprintf(fid,'P1 = App.Placement(Pos =(0,0,0))\n');
38     fprintf(fid,'P1.Rotation.Q = (0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 1.0)\n');
39     fprintf(fid,'P1.Base = points[0]\n');
40     fprintf(fid,'makewire("%s", points,Placement= P1)\n', ['Cell' num2str(j)]);
41     fprintf(fid,'FreeCAD.getDocument(''Wing'').getObject(''%s'').Placement = App.
        Placement(App.Vector(0.00,0.00,0.00),App.Rotation(App.Vector
        (0.00,0.00,1.00),0.00))\n', ['Cell' num2str(j)]);
42 end
43 fclose(fid);
44 end
```

2.9 Code S9: Run Region Growing

We developed this code to demonstrate how to use the *RegionGrowing* function in projects. In this code, users can mark a closed area inside the wing when importing an image. The code prints the coordinates of the boundary of that extracted cell.

Input: The input for this function is a binary image of the wing, which is obtained using Code S2 in line 3 for this purpose.

Output: The output of this function is *boundary*, which is an N-by-2 array containing the coordinates of the boundary of the selected region.

Code Description:

- **Line 3:** This line runs the *GetImage* function described in Code S2.
- **Lines 5-11:** In these lines, the code displays the imported image and waits for the user to click inside one region.
- **Line 12:** This line runs the *RegionGrowing* function, using the point chosen by the user by clicking inside the region as the initial point.
- **Lines 13-17:** These lines visualize the detected boundary and display the image after being processed by the *RegionGrowing* function.

Code S9: Developed code for running Region Growing code

```
1 function boundary = runRegionGrowing
2 %% Import Image / Binarization
3 [imageBinaryImage,~,~,imageHeight]=GetImage;
4 %% Region Growing
5 fig = figure('Name','Region Growing');
6 ax =gca(fig);
7 imshow(imageBinaryImage,'parent',ax)
8 title(ax,'Please click inside a desired domain')
9 roi = drawpoint(ax);
10 c = round(roi.Position(1));
11 r = round(roi.Position(2));
12 [~,n_white,im,boundary]=RegionGrowing(imageBinaryImage,r,c);
13 cla(ax)
14 imshow(im,'parent',ax)
15 hold(ax,'on')
16 plot(boundary(:,1),imageHeight-boundary(:,2),'color','r','linewidth',3,'linestyle', '-','parent',ax)
17 title(ax,['Area: ' num2str(n_white) 'px^2 '])
18 end
```

2.10 Code S10: Run WingSegment

This code is developed to demonstrate how WingSegment integrates various components to segment an insect wing image.

Code Description:

- **Line 3:** To initiate wing image segmentation, the first function is *GetImage* (Code S2).
- **Line 5:** If we begin with extracting junctions, the next code is *junctionDetection* (Code S5). This function uses *imageBinaryImage* as input from the *GetImage* function.
- **Lines 7-14:** These lines create the first figure and plot detected junctions.
- **Lines 16-18:** These lines visualize the skeletonized image.
- **Line 20:** In this line, the *veinDetection_SVD* function runs. It should be noted that prior to vein detection, the junction detection should be executed, as vein detection requires the location of junctions and the skeletonized image as input.
- **Lines 22-31:** These lines visualize detected veins using the SVD method.
- **Lines 33-42:** These lines also plot a heatmap of vein lengths detected with the SVD method.
- **Lines 44-46:** These lines generate a histogram related to the vein lengths extracted from the SVD method.
- **Lines 48-74:** These lines are analogous to lines 20-46 but for the PVD method.
- **Lines 76-81:** These lines illustrate the *cellSegment* function. For this function, the *GetImage* function needs to be executed beforehand because it requires the binary image as input.
- **Lines 83-96:** In these lines, we demonstrate how to generate heatmaps of the wing cells' area, length, and circularity distribution.
- **Lines 98-108:** These lines show how one can plot the extracted wing cells.
- **Line 110:** This line runs the *generateFreeCadModel* function. Note that this function can only be executed after extracting cells, as it requires *wingOutline* and *wingCells* as input.

Code S10: Integrating all functions to segment the wing

```
1 function runWingSegment
2 %% Import Image / Binarization
3 [imageBinaryImage,~,~,~]=GetImage;
4 %% Junction Detection / Wing Skeletonization
5 [junctions, skeletonizedImage]=junctionDetection(imageBinaryImage);
6 % Figure 1: Detected Junctions
7 fig1 = figure('Name','Detected Junctions');
8 ax1 = gca(fig1);
9 imshow(imageBinaryImage,'parent',ax1)
10 hold(ax1,'on')
11 xJunctions = junctions.c;
12 yJunctions = junctions.r;
13 plot(xJunctions, yJunctions, 'marker','o','markeredgecolor','r','markerfacecolor'
    , 'r','markersize',10,'parent',ax1,'linestyle','none')
14 axis(ax1,'equal')
15 % Figure 2: 'Skeletonized Image'
16 fig2 = figure('Name','Skeletonized Image');
17 ax2 = gca(fig2);
18 imshow(skeletonizedImage,'parent',ax2)
19 %% Sequential Vein Detection (SVD)
20 detectedVeins_SVD = veinDetection_SVD(skeletonizedImage, junctions);
21 % Figure 3: 'Detected Veins (SVD)'
22 fig3 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (SVD)');
```

```

23 ax3 =gca(fig3);
24 nVeins = length(detectedVeins_SVD.coordinate);
25 hold(ax3,'on')
26 for i = 1 : nVeins
27     xVeins = detectedVeins_SVD.coordinate{i}(:,1);
28     yVeins = size(imageBinaryImage,1)-detectedVeins_SVD.coordinate{i}(:,2);
29     plot(xVeins,yVeins,'linestyle','-','linewidth',3,'color','b','parent',ax3)
30 end
31 axis(ax3,'equal')
32 % Figure 4: 'Detected Veins (SVD)-Length Distribution)'
33 fig4 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (SVD)-Length Distribution');
34 ax4 =gca(fig4);
35 hold(ax4,'on')
36 for i = 1 : nVeins
37     veinColor = detectedVeins_SVD.Color(i,:);
38     xVeins = detectedVeins_SVD.coordinate{i}(:,1);
39     yVeins = size(imageBinaryImage,1)-detectedVeins_SVD.coordinate{i}(:,2);
40     plot(xVeins,yVeins,'linestyle','-','linewidth',3,'color',veinColor,'parent',
         ax4)
41 end
42 axis(ax4,'equal')
43 % Figure 5: Detected Veins (SVD)-Length Distribution Histogram
44 fig5 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (SVD)-Length Distribution Histogram');
45 ax5 =gca(fig5);
46 histogram(ax5,detectedVeins_SVD.length,10)
47 %% Parallel Vein Detection (PVD)
48 detectedVeins_PVD = veinDetection_PVD(skeletonizedImage,junctions);
49 % Figure 6: Detected Veins (PVD)
50 fig6 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (PVD)');
51 ax6 =gca(fig6);
52 nVeins = length(detectedVeins_PVD.coordinate);
53 hold(ax6,'on')
54 for i = 1 : nVeins
55     xVeins = detectedVeins_PVD.coordinate{i}(:,1);
56     yVeins = size(imageBinaryImage,1)-detectedVeins_PVD.coordinate{i}(:,2);
57     plot(xVeins,yVeins,'linestyle','-','linewidth',3,'color','b','parent',ax6)
58 end
59 axis(ax6,'equal')
60 % Figure 7: Detected Veins (PVD)-Length Distribution
61 fig7 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (PVD)-Length Distribution');
62 ax7 =gca(fig7);
63 hold(ax7,'on')
64 for i = 1 : nVeins
65     veinColor = detectedVeins_PVD.Color(i,:);
66     xVeins = detectedVeins_PVD.coordinate{i}(:,1);
67     yVeins = size(imageBinaryImage,1)-detectedVeins_PVD.coordinate{i}(:,2);
68     plot(xVeins,yVeins,'linestyle','-','linewidth',3,'color',veinColor,'parent',
         ax7)
69 end
70 axis(ax7,'equal')
71 % Figure 8: Detected Veins (PVD)-Length Distribution Histogram
72 fig8 = figure('Name','Detected Veins (PVD)-Length Distribution Histogram');
73 ax8 =gca(fig8);
74 histogram(ax8,detectedVeins_PVD.length,10)
75 %% Cell Segmentation
76 [ContourMatrix_Area,...
77     ContourMatrix_Length,...

```

```

78     ContourMatrix_Circularity,...
79     wingOutline,...
80     wingCells,...
81     wingInfo] = cellSegment(imageBinaryImage);
82 % Figure 9: Area Distribution Filled Contour
83 fig9 = figure('Name','Wing Cells Area Distribution Filled Contour');
84 ax9 =gca(fig9);
85 contourf(ax9,ContourMatrix_Area,100,'linestyle','none')
86 axis(ax9,'equal')
87 % Figure 10: Wing Cells Length Distribution Filled Contour
88 fig10 = figure('Name','Wing Cells Length Distribution Filled Contour');
89 ax10 =gca(fig10);
90 contourf(ax10,ContourMatrix_Length,100,'linestyle','none')
91 axis(ax10,'equal')
92 % Figure 11: Wing Cells Circularity Distribution Filled Contour
93 fig11 = figure('Name','Wing Cells Circularity Distribution Filled Contour');
94 ax11 =gca(fig11);
95 contourf(ax11,ContourMatrix_Circularity,100,'linestyle','none')
96 axis(ax11,'equal')
97 % Figure 12: Extracted Wing Cells
98 fig12 = figure('Name','Extracted Wing Cells');
99 ax12 =gca(fig12);
100 plot(wingOutline(:,1),wingOutline(:,2),'linewidth',2,'linestyle','-','color','b',
      'parent',ax12)
101 hold(ax12,'on')
102 nCells = length(wingCells);
103 for i = 1 : nCells
104     x = wingCells{i}(:,1);
105     y = wingCells{i}(:,2);
106     plot(x,y,'linewidth',2,'color','r','linestyle','-','parent',ax12,'linewidth'
      ,2)
107 end
108 axis(ax12,'equal')
109 %% Generate FreeCad Model
110 generateFreeCadModel(wingOutline,wingCells)
111 end

```

2.11 Interconnection of integrated functions within WingSegment

The flowchart in Figure S2 illustrates the sequence of operations in *WingSegment*. It begins with the *GetImage* function, and from there, both *RegionGrowing* and *junctionDetection* can start, with no priority between them. The *cellSegment* function also starts with *RegionGrowing*. Following *cellSegment*, the *generateFreeCadModel* function can be executed. Additionally, after running *junctionDetection*, the *veinDetection_PVD* and *veinDetection_SVD* functions can be invoked. The results obtained from *cellSegment*, *junctionDetection*, *veinDetection_PVD*, and *veinDetection_SVD* are integrated within *WingSegment*, resulting in the segmentation of the wing image.

Figure S2: The flowchart illustrating the interconnection of integrated functions within *WingSegment*.

4 Additional 3D-Printed Wings

Figure S4 illustrates extra examples showcasing the performance of WingSegment. Figure S4 provides additional examples that demonstrate the performance of WingSegment. The STL file for the wing in figure S4 is as follows:

- a, and b: Model S4.
- c, and d: Model S5.
- e, and f: Model S3.

Figure S4: Additional examples of 3D-printed/model wings: a) Damsel fly wing printed model, b) Damsel fly wing 3D model, c) Locust wing printed model, d) Locust wing 3D model, e) Scarlet Dragonfly forewing printed model, f) Scarlet Dragonfly wing 3D model.

5 Additional Quantitative Analysis of Insect Wing Morphology Using WingSegment

In this supplementary section, we present additional insights into the capabilities of WingSegment, our innovative software designed to analyze insect wing morphology comprehensively. Figures S5, S6, and S7 showcase the software's proficiency in characterizing the wings of a Damselfly, Locust, and Dragonfly, respectively. Each figure includes heatmaps illustrating wing cell area, length, and circularity, accompanied by corresponding box plots and histograms. This multi-faceted approach provides a detailed understanding of the geometric features inherent in the wings of different insect species.

Additionally, Figure S8 explores the length of venation patterns extracted from Damselfly, Locust, and Dragonfly wings in panels (a), (b), and (c), respectively. These heatmaps highlight the software's capacity to unravel the finer details of wing structures, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of insect morphology.

Figure S5: Morphometric Analysis of Damselfly Wing.

Figure S6: Exploring Locust Wing Morphology.

Figure S7: Dragonfly Wing Morphology Unveiled.

Figure S8: Panel (a), (b), and (c) present heatmaps depicting the length of venation patterns extracted from Damselfly, Locust, and Dragonfly wings, respectively.

6 Supplementary Files(Zenodo Repository)

This study contains supplementary files that are stored in the Zenodo repository and are accessible via the following link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10615544>

The following files will be found in the supplementary files:

6.1 Supplementary Codes

- Desktop App: This folder includes the installable WingSegment.exe file compatible with Windows computers.
- MATLAB App: This folder contains the MATLAB App file for installation as a MATLAB toolbox.
- Validation: This folder contains the custom code for manually counting wing cells and junctions.
- WingSegment Functions: This folder contains all supplementary codes introduced in section 2.

6.2 Supplementary Figures

- Figure S1: Manual and automated detection of cells and junctions in a Scarlet dragonfly forewing.
- Figure S2: The flowchart illustrating the interconnection of integrated functions within WingSegment.
- Figure S3: This figure illustrates a description of WingSegment's graphical user interface.

6.3 Supplementary Models

- Model S1: The 3D printable model of Honeybee wing.
- Model S2: The 3D printable model of Scarlet Dragonfly hindwing.
- Model S3: The 3D printable model of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing.
- Model S4: The 3D printable model of a Damselfly wing.
- Model S5: The 3D printable model of a Locust wing

6.4 Supplementary Sample Images

- Sample Image S1: Image of a Honeybee wing.
- Sample Image S2: Image of a Scarlet Dragonfly wing hindwing.
- Sample Image S3: Image of a Scarlet Dragonfly forewing.
- Sample Image S4: Image of a Damselfly wing.
- Sample Image S5: Image of a Locust wing.

6.5 Supplementary Validation Files

- File S1: The coordinate of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing cells centroids, extracted manually using Code S1.
- File S2: The coordinate of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing junctions, extracted manually using Code S1.
- File S3: The coordinate of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing cells centroids, extracted automatically using WingSegment.
- File S4: The coordinate of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing junctions, extracted automatically using WingSegment.
- File S5: This file contains all information related to the validation of WingSegment.

6.6 Supplementary Videos

- Video S1: Manual counting of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing cells.
- Video S2: Manual counting of Scarlet Dragonfly forewing junctions.
- Video S3: Region Growing visualization.
- Video S4: Parallel Vein Detection (PVD) visualization.
- Video S5: Sequential Vein Detection (PVD) visualization.
- Video S6: A quick demo of WingSegment.
- Video S7: From WingSegment to FreeCAD. This video introduces how to import the generated model.